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CREATING KNOWLEDGE IN DESIGN THINKING

THE RELATIONSHIP OF PROCESS STEPS AND KNOWLEDGE TYPES

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the design thinking process in terms of its capability to create design knowledge. For this purpose, we refer to a typology that suggests four different types of design knowledge as well as three interjacent transitions. According to this typology, design knowledge can be represented in physical artifacts, as tacit gut feeling, as codified knowledge, or as testable theories. We analyze the different process steps of design thinking through extensive case studies of design thinking projects in an educational context and map them to the different levels of this typology. The work presented in this article contributes to a better understanding of the working mechanisms of the design thinking process.

Keywords: Design Thinking, Design Education, Design Knowledge

INTRODUCTION

Design thinking is a specific method to solve wicked problems (Buchanan, 1992; Rittel, 1972) and to generate innovative solutions, based on a user-centered approach with multi-disciplinary teams. Design thinking—originally introduced and shaped by the design consultancy IDEO (Brown, 2008; Kelley & Littman, 2001)—is becoming more and more popular. There are numerous educational institutions that offer programs in design thinking—such as the Hasso Plattner Institute of Design in Stanford or the Rotman School of Management in Toronto—, and it is applied in R&D departments of companies to foster innovation. Since it is the idea of design thinking to create knowledge, and specifically innovative concepts, the question arises, how knowledge is

represented in the process of design thinking, and how new knowledge is being created.

There has been a lot of research about design thinking in general (e.g. Brown, 2008; Brown, 2009; Dunne & Martin, 2006; Kelley & Littman, 2001; Kelley & Littman, 2005; Martin, 2009; Plattner, Meinel et al., 2011; Plattner, Meinel et al., 2009), but a detailed analysis about the actual working mechanisms of the method has not been conducted, so far. We provide such a detailed analysis on at least one aspect of the working mechanisms of design thinking—how design knowledge is represented and created in the process.

Our research is based on case studies of different design thinking projects in an educational context. We analyze the design thinking process as it is practiced at the School of Design Thinking (“HPI D-School”) of the Hasso Plattner Institute in Potsdam, Germany in terms of its capability to create new design knowledge. Specifically, we suggest a theoretical model of the design thinking process that is mapping the particular process steps to types of design knowledge. The result provides insights about which type of knowledge is mainly used in a specific phase of a process. This could help design thinking students, teachers, practitioners, and researchers to better understand the working mechanisms of the process, and to improve or modify the process to fit their specific requirements.

This paper is structured as follows: First, we describe the typology of design knowledge by Müller and Thoring (2010) that we used as a basis for the work presented in this article. The second section covers a brief description of the design thinking process of the HPI D-School. The third section provides a

detailed description of our used methodology. While the fourth section – the main part of this article – introduces our proposed theoretical model, in which we are mapping different types of design knowledge to the process steps of design thinking. Finally, we analyze and interpret the suggested model and the resulting implications on design thinking, and discuss possible contributions for design thinking education and practice, as well as limitations and future work.

DESIGN KNOWLEDGE FRAMEWORK

In order to be able to analyze knowledge representations within the design thinking process, a deep understanding of different types of design knowledge as well as their specific characteristics and representations is required. Since the last millennia, philosophers and scientists created numerous theories and definitions of what knowledge is (for an overview see e.g. Maier (2002)). In the classical philosophical definition of Plato (2008), knowledge is described as “justified, true belief”. This definition, however, is too narrow for our purpose, because it excludes all knowledge that cannot easily be justified, like gut feeling or design intuition. The semiotic view (Aamodt & Nygård, 1995), defines knowledge as all information that is connected with other information, embedded in a context, and applicable to achieve a goal. Thus, knowledge provides the ability to perform effective decisions and actions—that means it has a pragmatic dimension.

In this paper, we refer to a typology that suggests four different types of design knowledge as well as three interjacent transitions, see Figure 1 (Müller & Thoring, 2010; Popper, 1972; Radermacher, 1996). It follows a broad, pragmatic view of knowledge, wherein all patterns that enable actions or decisions are called knowledge (Radermacher, 1996). According to this typology, there are four levels of design knowledge: A – the physical level, in which knowledge is represented as physical instantiations or signals (“Design Artifacts”), B – the neuronal level, in which knowledge is tacit (“Design Intuition”), C – the symbolic level, in which knowledge is codified (“Design Rational”), and D – the model level, in which knowledge is represented as testable theories (“Design Theories”).

The four levels are physically building up on each other, which means that each level also incorporates aspects of the respective preceding level(s). This does not suggest any prioritization of the levels—e.g. explicit (symbolic) knowledge is not better or more important than tacit (neuronal) knowledge, but it cannot work without tacit as well as physical aspects. The transitions between these four levels describe how knowledge is transformed from on level to the next or previous level, which is also a possibility to create new knowledge.

In the remainder of this article we try to map these four types of design knowledge to the process steps of design thinking.

Levels of Design Knowledge	Type	Representation
D Model Level (Models and Theories)	Design Theories	Testable Design Theories (e.g. Golden Ratio)
Transition C↔D 		
C Symbolic Level (Explicit Knowledge)	Design Rational	Design Terminology, Design Rules (e.g. technical Drawings, Manuals)
Transition B↔C 		
B Neuronal Level (Tacit Knowledge)	Design Intuition	Design Intuition, Skills (e.g. Master-Apprentice, Trial-and-Error)
Transition A↔B 		
A Physical Level (3D Form & Instantiations)	Design Artifacts	Form, „Gestalt“, Embodied Knowledge (e.g. Bionics)

Figure 1. The Typology of Design Knowledge, adapted from (Müller & Thoring, 2010).

DESIGN THINKING PROCESS

We believe that the effectiveness of the design thinking process can be explained by the creation, representation, and testing of specific types of design knowledge according to different process steps. The design thinking process at the HPI D-Schools consists of 6 steps: “Understand”, “Observe”, “Point of View”, “Ideate”, “Prototype”, and “Test”, which are usually conducted in an iterative way (see Figure 2.)

Figure 2. The Design Thinking Process of the HPI D-School in Potsdam, Germany; used with permission (Plattner, Meinel et al., 2009)

However, this model of the design thinking process is quite rough. To illustrate what is actually happening in each of the phases, we suggest a more detailed description of several steps, such as “Interview” (as part of “Observe”), “Storytelling” and “Synthesis” (as part of the “Point of View”), “Develop Brainstorming Question” and “Idea Selection” (as part of “Ideation”), and “Test Observe”, “Test Interview”, and “Reflect/Iterate” (as part of the “Test” step). See (Thoring & Müller, 2011a) for a detailed description of the particular process steps.

METHODOLOGY

The foundations of this article are based on case studies of five projects in a design thinking education context, namely at the School of Design Thinking of the Hasso-Plattner-Institute Potsdam, Germany. Over a period of three years, we observed several student projects and analyzed them in terms of the way information was exchanged, stored, or created within the student teams.

SELECTION OF CASES

We chose five specific projects for our case study (see Table 1), according to the following criteria: 1) experience of the students, 2) involvement of industry partner institutions, and 3) diversity of the design challenges. The selected cases were scheduled at an advanced stage of the study program, when the students already had some experiences with short design thinking exercises. The selected 6-weeks projects were scheduled at the end of the first semester, and the 12-weeks project were taking place over the entire second semester. Both types of projects had external project partners involved who acted as some kind of client. This realistic setting allowed for a better analysis of the role of knowledge than mere test exercises. And finally, the selected cases were representing a broad diversity, both in scope, cooperation partners, and also in the results (partners were NGOs as well as industry corporations, or governmental institutions; results ranged from physical products to digital applications). This diversity suggests that specific observations concerning the representation and transfer of knowledge are independent from project topics or scopes. All projects were conducted by a team of 5 to 6 students. The 6-week projects were

conducted by two teams who worked simultaneously on the same challenge in a competitive manner. This provided the possibility to crosscheck the observed results. We analyzed 5 projects conducted by 8 different teams.

Case	Challenge	Dur. #	Industry Partner
1 People Trusting People	How might we establish trust between friends in lending situations?	12 weeks 1 team	Telekom Germany (Industry)
2 Airport Security	How might we assure the security standards at passenger airports and increase efficiency and convenience of passenger handling during check-in?	12 weeks 1 team	ZAB (Gov.)
3 Empowering Participatory Politics	How might we help inexperienced internet users to make meaningful contributions to political debates and processes?	6 weeks 2 teams	Res Publica (NGO)
4 Modern Office Communication	How might we design an office system to handle mail management processes that facilitates the every day communication activities of office employees?	6 weeks 2 teams	Francotyp Postalia (Industry)
5 Book Recommendations	How might we help readers to discover those 50 personally relevant book releases each year?	6 weeks 2 teams	Elstner-tainment + WDR (Industry)

Table 1. Overview of selected Cases.

DATA SOURCES

For each step of the design thinking process, the following data sources were observed and analyzed: the behavior of individual team members as well as interactions within the team, verbal expressions, written output (such as ideas on post-it notes or texts in the project wiki), visual output (such as diagrams, sketches, photos etc.), prototypes, and the use of the environment (such as whiteboards or post-it notes) as knowledge repositories.

RESEARCH PROCEDURE

We conducted the case study based on two independent data analysis methods: one researcher acted as a coach and was therefore involved in the project and was able to extract first hand insights from the team (participatory observation). The second researcher acted as an external (independent) observer. He checked the results afterwards and was therefore able to act as verification. Any possible bias caused by the involvement of the first researcher could therefore be compensated to some extent. This research

procedure was split and cross applied: one researcher was the main teacher for one half of the projects and additionally acted as an external observer for the remaining projects, and vice versa.

RESULT: THEORETICAL MODEL

The consolidated results of the case studies are shown in Figure 3. The observations from the analyzed cases were mapped to the before-mentioned framework of design knowledge. In the following section we explain in detail, why we placed certain observations in the respective level or transition of the knowledge framework.

Understand:

In this step the students performed mainly desk research. Knowledge that was represented in explicit form as books, articles, or websites (level C) was internalized. The goal was to ‘become an expert’ on the topic, which creates new knowledge for the team (transition C→B). As a result of that specific process step, knowledge was represented as internalized, tacit knowledge among the students (Level B).

Observe:

Out in the field, the students performed user research. The knowledge was present in the form of physical signals (level A) that had to be observed (filtered) by the students (transition A→B). As the output of this step, the knowledge was represented as tacit knowledge (level B).

Interview:

Although part of the user research as well, the interviewing activities showed different results than the observations. First, the knowledge was tacit within the interviewees (level B) and it had to be extracted and externalized by the students through questioning and also through interpreting the answers (transition B→C). As the output of this step, the knowledge was represented as explicit knowledge, such as recordings or transcripts of the interviews (level C).

Storytelling:

In this step of the process, the internalized (level B) knowledge from the two previous activities was

externalized through group discussions, printing photos, and writing down the insights (transition B→C). The insights were shared among the team to generate new knowledge for the group. Insights were represented in codified forms, either written on post-it notes, as sketches, as photos, or as a spoken narrative (all level C).

Synthesis:

The codified knowledge (level C) from the previous storytelling step is now re-structured (filtered and rearranged) in order to create a theory about the problem and/or user needs. Relevant information is distinguished from the irrelevant, e.g. through clustering insights or arranging information in frameworks (transition C→D). Possible outcomes of this step are 2-axis mappings, Venn diagrams, mind maps, causal graphs, or personas, etc. which then represents knowledge in the form of a model (level D), which places it beyond mere explicit knowledge.

Point of View:

The Point of View is actually describing the outcome of the Synthesis step. This is the theory (in the form of a model, level D) that students develop about the user’s needs and the problems to solve, and which determines the future direction of the project.

Brainstorming Question:

The Brainstorming question is derived directly from the previous Point of View. The theory about the problem (level D) is transformed into a question that verbally phrases a possible solution space (transition D→C), and then presents that information in explicit form (level C).

Ideation:

The generation of solution ideas is the actual ‘creative’ step of the process. Ideas are developed through ideation techniques such as brainstorming or brainwriting. In this step, many different knowledge representations come together: The brainstorming question is explicit, as well as the brainstorming rules (level C). However, also intuitive knowledge such as internalized assumptions about the problem and the user’s needs might come into play (level B). Ideas can be created by combining explicit knowledge (C→C), by internalizing explicit

knowledge (transition C→B) and by externalizing tacit knowledge (transition B→C). This phenomenon is also described by Nonaka (1994). The output of this specific process step is usually ideas written on post-it notes (level C).

Idea Selection:

Selecting ideas is mainly taking place on a rational basis (level C). Explicit knowledge (ideas written or sketched on post-it notes) is given as the input for this process step. Rational criteria (arguments, level C) are provided for or against certain ideas (such as 'originality' or 'usefulness'), and finally as the output of this step there is a selection of one or a few ideas, again in explicit form (all level C). Tacit knowledge, such as intuition about the potential success of ideas can be transformed into explicit knowledge, based on logical arguments and discussion (transition B→C). However, we observed that the students sometimes seemed to vote for certain ideas on an irrational basis: someone just 'likes' an idea without being able to explain, why. This could be explained either with design expertise based on experience

('gut feeling' of an expert), or with personal bias of the students, as they tend to like their own ideas more than other's (both being placed at level B).

Prototyping:

Prototyping means the visualization of an idea by the means of modelmaking, detailed sketching, paper-prototyping, roleplaying, videos, interactive click dummies, or the like. The idea is inserted as internalized knowledge by the students—they had to understand and embody the concept in order to be able to prototype it (level B). The internalized knowledge was then being transformed into a physical representation of the concept (transition B→A). Therefore the concept hypotheses are "frozen" in the artifact (Müller & Thoring, 2011), which means the design knowledge is represented on level A.

Test / Observe:

When the prototyped idea is tested, there are two types of knowledge to be considered: First, the reactions of the test users and their interactions with

Figure 3. Mapping of design thinking process steps to knowledge types and transitions.

● = knowledge creation; i = knowledge representation as input; o = knowledge representation as output

the prototype had to be observed and interpreted. As in the previous observation step, the knowledge was present in the form of physical signals (level A) that had to be observed (filtered) by the students (transition A→B). As a result of that step, the knowledge was represented as tacit knowledge (level B).

Test / Interview:

Second, the test users were interviewed and questioned about their impressions. As in the research interview, the knowledge was first tacit within the interviewees (level B), and it had to be extracted and externalized by the students through questioning and also through interpreting the answers (transition B→C). Finally, the knowledge was represented as explicit knowledge, such as quotes and transcripts of the interviews (level C).

Reflect / Iterate:

Reflection on the insights from the user tests mainly occurred based on logical arguments. Pros and cons of the developed prototype were discussed verbally among the team members. As an output of this step, a decision was made, if and how to iterate the concept, based on explicit knowledge evaluation (both level C). New knowledge was created by validating or falsifying previously made design assumptions (also level C).

IMPLICATIONS

Design thinking is a process to generate new design knowledge, and to test hypotheses in early stages of the process. The sooner the developed concepts can be validated or falsified, the sooner the process can be finished or iterated and improved, respectively. The question arises, how such hypotheses are developed. While analyzing the observed data sources from the 5 projects (respectively 8 teams), and mapping them to the before-mentioned knowledge framework, several insights could be determined that are described in the following section.

KNOWLEDGE REPRESENTATION

The model presented in the previous section (Figure 3) shows that in the design thinking process most of the knowledge representations are located on the

levels B and C (tacit and explicit knowledge). Level D knowledge (testable theories and models) is only present in one specific phase of the process—between the synthesis and the Point of View, resulting in the brainstorming question. Level A (physical) knowledge is only present two times—at the beginning of the process (research observation), and towards the end of the process (prototyping and test observation). These are the only touch points with the 'real' physical world.

We think that for design thinking practitioners and students it is important to understand what kind of knowledge types they are dealing with. If, for example, the knowledge within the users is represented in tacit form, just asking for their opinion will not generate the desired insights. Therefore, extracting tacit knowledge seems to be one of the main challenges of design thinking.

KNOWLEDGE CREATION

As the presented model shows, new knowledge is mainly created in one of the three transitions, by transforming one type of knowledge to another one. This happens either by filtering signals from the physical level or adjusting these filters (between levels A and B), by internalizing or externalizing knowledge (between levels B and C), and by theory formation or creating new concepts (between levels C and D). However, there are a few exceptions to this phenomenon: In the Point of View step, the students created theories about the users' needs, which is placed on level D. In the ideation step, knowledge is created also by recombining existing explicit knowledge within level C (C→C), additionally to transforming knowledge by externalizing and internalizing. The idea selection occurs partly based on intuition (level B), even if this was identified as problematic. Idea selection should preferably be rational and not intuitive (at least in educational contexts). Students should be aware of the possible consequences of intuitive decisions. And finally the reflection and iteration is taking place solely on a rational basis (level C), because the learnings from the testing are reflected and discussed based on logical arguments.

It is almost always necessary to transform the tacit knowledge somehow in order to create new knowledge from it, either by making it explicit ($B \rightarrow C$) or by making it tangible ($B \rightarrow A$). We suggest further research on that specific aspect, to analyze the impact of socialization, such as culture, team spirit, or trial-and-error ($B \rightarrow B$) on creating new knowledge in design thinking. Since these aspects are quite distinct in design thinking, this might be an interesting field for future research. In (Thoring & Müller, 2011b), we used an evolutionary approach for understanding how design thinking is creating knowledge.

KNOWLEDGE TESTING

Testing is identified as an important factor to generate new knowledge. Specific assumptions about the problem and the user's needs are validated or falsified. During testing, students should be able to distinguish between test interview and test observation. Both require different use of knowledge. Reflecting the insights from the user test is a crucial part of the design thinking process. For example: if the prototype fails, this does not necessarily mean, that the user needs were not correctly identified. Therefore, a qualitative analysis is necessary to identify the reason of the failure.

PROCESS STRUCTURE

The whole process is mapped as an up-and-down movement between the different knowledge types. This could also be interpreted as a sequence of induction and deduction. In the inductive part (up movement) concrete observations (level A) and user needs (level B) are condensed into an abstract framework (level D). For that framework a concrete prototype (level A) is created and tested, which represents the deductive part (down movement).

COMPARISON WITH NONAKA'S SECI MODEL

Nonaka (1994) distinguishes between explicit and tacit knowledge. His definition diverts from the original definition of Polanyi (1966), because Nonaka states that tacit knowledge has uncodifiable (pure tacit knowledge) and codifiable parts (implicit knowledge) (Nonaka & von Krogh, 2009). Furthermore, Nonaka (1994) differentiates between four different ways to create new knowledge:

- 1) Internalization, which means transforming knowledge from explicit to tacit ($C \rightarrow B$).
- 2) Externalization, which means transforming knowledge from tacit to explicit ($B \rightarrow C$).
- 3) Socialization, which means learning from relevant environments, e.g. in a master-apprentice-relationship ($B \rightarrow B$).
- 4) Recombination of explicit knowledge ($C \rightarrow C$).

In large parts, this concept is in-line with our identified forms of knowledge creation: we also observed the creation of new design knowledge based on externalizing tacit and internalizing explicit knowledge ($B \rightarrow C$ and $C \rightarrow B$), as well as the recombination of explicit knowledge ($C \rightarrow C$).

Interesting are the differences between our model and Nonaka's model. Nonaka's third option—socialization within level B ($B \rightarrow B$)—was not often observed in our case studies. Only in the idea selection step we noticed that students made decisions on idea selection based on intuitive feelings, without being able to explicitly explain those decisions. We identified this as a critical point, since students usually do not have enough experience from past projects to judge the potential of specific ideas just based on their gut feeling. However, it seems logical, that also idea generation might be possible through combination of level B knowledge. Most of us are familiar with the feeling that tacit knowledge is somehow 'breeding' inside us, but we are not able to verbalize it or to bring the idea out of our minds. Since this is difficult—if not impossible—to observe (one cannot observe what is going on in someone else's mind), we didn't place this in our model. This phenomenon becomes visible, once the idea becomes tangible when we are not thinking about the problem at all—e.g. when we suddenly have an idea while taking a shower. We can only assume that the tacit knowledge has been working and creating new concepts in our minds, without us noticing it. Nonaka describes this as socialization. Being in relevant environments as well as a master-apprentice relationship might add to the possibility to create new design knowledge intuitively. Compared to Nonaka (1994), we also identified some additional aspects as relevant for knowledge creation that he does not mention. As

mentioned before, our model shows that new knowledge is also being created by transforming physical knowledge into tacit knowledge or vice versa ($B \rightarrow A$ or $A \rightarrow B$), e.g. when prototyping ideas or when filtering signals from the environment. And this can also be achieved by theory-building and concept formation ($C \rightarrow D$ or $D \rightarrow C$).

DISCUSSION

There are numerous publications about design thinking (e.g. Brown, 2008; Brown, 2009; Dunne & Martin, 2006), but a detailed analysis of its working mechanisms has not been conducted, so far. In this article we suggest a mapping of different knowledge types to the process steps of design thinking, and try to explain how knowledge is represented and how new knowledge is being created in each step. Therefore this article contributes to a better understanding of the design thinking process, so that it might help educators to better teach design thinking principles, as well as practitioners to improve their design thinking projects. Our findings are based on extensive case studies of 5 design thinking projects in an educational context.

The goal of this article is to understand design thinking as a knowledge creation and testing process, as well as to understand for each step what kind of knowledge is created and how. It becomes clear that transforming knowledge from one type to another is crucial to create new knowledge. Students should be aware of this possibility and reflect on their process, in order to strategically create new design knowledge.

LIMITATIONS

One limitation of this study is that we only analyzed design thinking projects in one educational institute. This limits the generalizability of our findings.

FUTURE WORK

Future work should compare our findings with other educational organizations and with design thinking projects outside the educational context. Further research on the topic might also involve a comparison of our suggested model with other design processes, as well as a comparison with the design thinking process as it is applied by practitioners,

such as the design consultancy IDEO. Moreover, we see a specific deficit in the analysis of what Nonaka calls 'socialization' (knowledge creation based on tacit and intuitive knowledge: $B \rightarrow B$). On the one hand, students are supposed to make their own experiences to create intuition, but on the other hand, developing that specific expertise might also be supported by other aspects. Developing such an intuition and to extract tacit knowledge might be one of the challenges of design thinking. Further research on that topic is planned.

CONCLUSION

Of course it is possible to execute the several steps of the design thinking process without understanding what is happening there and how new knowledge is being created. But this is unsatisfactory for two reasons: First, there is a high likelihood that the process is applied wrongly. Second, without proper reflection the process can only be improved by trial-and-error.

If design thinking wants to reach the status of a scientific field, it has to reflect on the working mechanisms of the process, in order to explain and to improve how designers think and work. This article contributes to this goal by offering an explanation about the working mechanisms of design thinking regarding its capability to create new design knowledge. According to Schön's "Reflective Practitioner" (Schön, 1984), we see the main contribution of this article in the stimulation of reflecting the design thinking process.

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